

Comparison Of Machine Learning Approaches In Arabic Tweeps Gender Prediction

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Abstract: In this paper, we present our approach for profiling Arabic authors on twitter, based on their tweets. We consider here the gender of an Arabic author as an important trait to be predicted. For this purpose, many indicators, feature vectors and machine learning-based classifiers were implemented. The results of these classifiers were compared to find out the best gender prediction model. The best prediction model was obtained using SMO classifier with word 1-3 grams and the used punctuation marks as feature vector.

Index Terms: Author Profiling, Gender Detection, Machine Learning, Social Media Analysis, Arabic Text Mining.

1. INTRODUCTION

Author profiling on social media is a method of analyzing the author writings on social media in order to uncover different traits of the author (e.g. gender, dialect and age) based on stylistic or content-based features. This method aims at taking advantage of a huge volume of data generated every second by a huge number of authors [1]. This has obvious benefits in the domain of social media analysis, such as in marketing and promotion campaigns, as well as in the security areas. With the birth and rise of social media [2], internet users in the Arab world were quick to react to this new technology and to utilize all what social media offer to connect, communicate and share information with others using Arabic language. Concerning gender of tweeps (Twitter users), twitter does not collect users' self-reported gender as do other social media sites (e.g., Facebook and Google+) [3]. Such information could be useful for targeting a specific audience for advertising, personalizing content, and for legal investigation. Topics and style of writing vary depending on the author gender (males and females). Males could be interested in sports, politics and economy, whereas females could be interested in fashion and celebrity news. In Arabic, words suffixes and prefixes differ between males and females, for example: "تشاركين" "t\$Arkyn" word for second person female vs. "تشارك" "t\$Ark" word for second person male. Moreover, females tend more to use emojis, whereas males may tend to write textual tweets. These differences could be used as indicators when developing a gender prediction model for Arab tweeps. In the rest of this paper, a brief of related works are summarized in section 2. In section 3, we present our methodology that includes: the characteristics of training and testing data, the features used for the developed model, and a step-by-step approach to build the prediction model. In section 4, a brief discussion of the results is addressed. At the end, insights for the future and a short summary are presented.

2 RELATED WORKS

Author gender identification is a classification problem that could be solved using various approaches. These approaches are based on the selected features extracted from the authors' writings, and the classifier used in the development of the

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prediction model. Features used in gender identification problem are content-based and style-based features [4]. In content-based features, character n-grams and word n-grams are widely used. Guillaume Kheng et al. in [5] used word uni-grams and bi-grams. Iliia Markov et al. in [6] combined character n-grams and word n-grams with values of 3-4 for typed characters, 3-7 for untyped characters and 2-3 for words, respectively. In untyped characters, n-gram types are ignored (e.g. 'the' as a whole word is no different from 'the' in the middle of a word), but in typed characters, n-grams of different types are distinguished (e.g. n-grams may be suffixes, punctuations, words etc.). Similarly, Alina Maria Ciobanu et al. in [7] combined 1-6 character n-grams and 1-2 word n-grams. In [8, 9], tf-idf n-grams were combined with word embedding, and with 2-gram characters in the beginning and ending, respectively. Many features selection criteria have been used: gain ratio [10], bag-of-words [11, 12], the 100 most discriminant words per class from a list of 500 topic words [13], and latent semantic analysis LSA [5]. In style-based features, character flooding (i.e. lengthened words) and emoticons or/and laughter expressions [11, 14] were commonly used. Iliia Markov et al. in [6] also combined domain names that are used in links, with different kinds of n-grams. Yaritza Adame-Arcia1 et al. in [11] combined emotional features such as: emotions, appraisal, admiration, positive/negative emoticons, and positive/negative words. Matej Martinc et al. in [15] used emojis and sentiment words. Concerning classification algorithms, most researchers used traditional machine learning algorithms such as logistic regression [8, 15, 16], SVMs [5, 6, 7, 12, 17, 18, 19], and distance-based methods [10, 11, 13]. Some researchers employed deep learning techniques for this purpose. For example, Don Kodyan et al. in [20] applied Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), whereas Nils Schaetti in [9] and Sebastian Sierra et al. in [21] used Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). Finally, Marc Franco-Salvador et al. in [22] applied Deep Averaging Networks.

3 OUR METHODOLOGY

In this section, we describe the dataset used in this work, and the features tested for the prediction model. The proposed model is explained in detail hereafter, including: data pre-processing, features extraction, features filtering and the algorithms with their evaluation criteria.

3.1 Dataset

In our research, we used training dataset from PAN conference 2017 [4]. One of PAN 2017 tasks was about Arabic tweeps profiling according to their gender. This data consists

The highest F1Train (91.4%) is achieved in experiments 6, 9, 11 and 12. We notice that SMO classifier with UniGram, BiGram and TriGram feature vector produced the best results in the training phase compared to other experiments. It seems that males and females differ in using words, and expressions composed of two and three words, e.g. "مش فاكرة" "m\$ fAkrp", "مش عارفة شو" "m\$ EAf \$w" for females, "مش فاكر" "m\$ fAkr", "مش عارف شو" "m\$ EAf \$w" for males, thus these features led to the best result. Even simple words gave good result (88%) in experiment 1 in comparison to Stem (82.4%), Lemma (83.5%) and CNNGram (84.9%) using the same SMO classifier. The character 2-7 grams made good result in experiment 4 with SMO classifier (84.9%), as the prefixes and suffixes are different between the two genders, e.g. females add "ين" "yn", "انت" "At" to the verbs and nouns respectively but males none. Finally, adding LHM, ATL and TPM in experiments 9, 11 and 12 respectively to the best feature vector preserved the F1Train.

4.2 Comparison Using Testing Data

To compare the different approaches, we used the testing data (160000 Arabic tweets written by 1600 authors) for evaluating the previous results. Table 2 shows the results.

TABLE 2

F1TEST COMPARISON

#	Feature Vector	SVM-P	SMO	RF	NB
1	UniGram	67.1%	71.1%	76.0%	69.0%
2	Stem	66.5%	54.7%	70.1%	61.4%
3	CNNGram	71.1%	76.4%	70.9%	68.3%
4	Lemma	69.6%	68.7%	73.9%	67.1%
5	UniGram + Stem	72.8%	70.8%	75.5%	68.0%
6	UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	63.8%	73.2%	75.9%	69.1%
7	POS+UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	74.0%	76.3%	74.7%	69.9%
8	Stem+UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	73.2%	72.2%	74.5%	68.2%
9	LHM+UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	65.3%	73.2%	75.7%	69.1%
10	LEN+UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	64.0%	73.4%	76.6%	69.0%
11	ATL+UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	64.2%	72.9%	75.5%	69.1%
12	TPM+UniGram+BiGram+TriGram	66.1%	76.9%	73.1%	69.1%

Table 2 shows that the highest F1Test (76.9%) is achieved in experiment 12 using SMO classifier with tweet punctuation marks and word 1-3 grams as feature vector. It seems that usage of punctuation marks differs between males and females; dataset confirms that males use punctuation marks more than females. Table 3 shows the confusion matrix that is corresponding to the best prediction model.

TABLE 3

THE CONFUSION MATRIX FOR THE BEST MODEL

	Male	Female
Male	599	201
Female	169	631

5CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented our study in author profiling of Arabic tweeps concerning gender trait. We trained several models using various features and classifiers to find the best model for predicting author gender. We found that using SMO classifier with word UniGram, BiGram and TriGram and tweets

punctuation marks as a feature vector led to the best model with F1Train (91.4%) and F1Test (76.9%). It will be worth investigating more features that could distinguish between males and females, such as: type of written topics, special words and emojis, type of shared links, etc. Moreover, we intend to study the effect of using deep learning algorithms for Arabic dialects classification in case of availability a huge dataset collected from Arabic writers.

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